

Genetic Variation and Influence of Quantitative Traits on Crossability Between PBR Cowpea and TVu-17327 Accession

Abiola Toyin Ajayi¹, Richard Omeiza¹, Oluwasijibomi Charlse Ogunremi², Abdulfaruk Aliu¹

¹Plant Breeding Unit, Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko, Ondo State; ²Agricultural Biotechnology Department, National Biotechnology Research and Development Agency, Abuja, Nigeria

Corresponding Author: Omeizarichard04@gmail.com

Abstract

The cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp) encounters challenges, notably susceptibility to the pod borer (*Maruca vitrata*), exacerbated by limited genetic diversity due to its self-pollinating nature. This study examined crossability between the pod borer-resistant SAMPEA-20T and susceptible TVu-17327 cowpea accessions. Conducted at Adekunle Ajasin University, Nigeria, the experiment employed polythene pots and meticulous pollination procedures. Significant variability was observed among crosses, particularly in pod-related traits. Direct crosses involved 97 flowers, yielding 1 to 3 pods per plant. Pod set percentage ranged from 11.10% to 50%, with pod length varying from 10.30 to 19.20 cm. Average seeds per pod, seed weight, and days to pod maturity ranged from 7 to 17, 0.10 to 0.40 g, and 37 to 46 days, respectively, with coefficients of variation between 31.40% in the number of flowers crossed (NFC) and 77.43% in the percentage of pod set. Reciprocal crosses displayed similar variability, with mean values of 6.13 flowers crossed per plant, 0.87 pod set, 12.43% pod set, and 9.71 cm average pod length, and coefficients of variation of 37.42% (NFC) and 85.76% (number of pod set). The study emphasizes substantial variability between SAMPEA-20T and TVu-17327, stressing the importance of integrating genetic and morphological factors in breeding programs to bolster cowpea productivity and resilience to biotic stresses in Nigeria. F₁ hybrids from these crosses warrant further assessment in subsequent generations to identify traits associated with pod borer resistance and susceptibility, aiding in optimizing cowpea productivity.

Keywords: Cowpea, Crossability, Genetic diversity, Pod Borer, Resilience

Introduction

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp), commonly known as "black-eyed pea," is a warm-season legume crop originating in Africa and cultivated for over 5,000 years, making it one of the world's oldest crops (Wiersema and León, 2013). Known for its resilience and drought tolerance, cowpea thrives in diverse agro-ecological zones, particularly arid and semi-arid climates (Sanginga *et al.*, 2003).

Culturally and nutritionally significant, cowpea serves as a staple food in many African countries, providing essential protein, fiber, vitamins (such as folate), and minerals (including iron and potassium) (Ndiaye *et al.*, 2017). In agriculture, cowpea plays a crucial role as a cover crop and in intercropping systems, enhancing soil fertility through nitrogen fixation. Its ability to withstand challenging conditions, such as drought and soil degradation, underscores its importance in sustainable farming practices (Ehlers and Hall, 1997). The crop's limited genetic variability, primarily due to its self-pollinating nature, and the lack of improved varieties capable of withstanding environmental conditions exacerbate these vulnerabilities, resulting in yields often below their potential and economic losses for farmers (Ajayi *et al.*, 2014; Ajetomobi and Abiodun, 2010). Enhancing the genetic base of cowpea is crucial for improving its productivity and resilience.

Genetic techniques are essential for developing crop varieties with desirable traits such as higher yields, pest resistance, and environmental adaptability (Tester and Langridge, 2010). GMOs like PBR cowpea or BT cowpea offer a source of desirable genes to revolutionize agriculture by allowing precise

manipulation of an organism's genetic makeup, leading to increased yields and reduced chemical inputs (Brookes & Barfoot, 2018).

Genetic variation provides the raw material for developing improved crop traits (Lopes-Caitar *et al.*, 2013). By selecting parent plants with desirable traits and compatible genetic backgrounds, breeders can achieve successful hybridization (Doebley *et al.*, 2006). Crossability, the ability of different genotypes to interbreed and produce fertile offspring, is fundamental for introducing genetic diversity and developing hybrid varieties with enhanced traits (Acquaah, 2012). This process increases adaptability to changing conditions, pests, and diseases (Gur and Zamir, 2004) and allows for the creation of hybrids that exhibit superior yield and quality (Hochholdinger and Hoecker, 2007). Moreover, crossability accelerates breeding programs by combining desired traits from different sources, reducing the development time for new varieties (Melchinger *et al.*, 2018), and harnessing plant genetic diversity for agricultural improvement. Therefore, the present study was aimed at investigating the magnitude of crossability between a pod borer resistant and a susceptible accession of cowpea, assessing direct and reciprocal crossability between two accessions of cowpea and determining the extent of the influence of morphological traits on the crossability of two accessions of cowpea.

Materials and methods

Two accessions of cowpea used for the study, SAMPEA 20T and TVu-17327, which is an improved variety with brown seed coat color, were obtained from National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA), Abuja and from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan, respectively.

The experiment was conducted at a screen house in the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko, Nigeria. Polythene pots were utilized for planting, and daily watering was implemented to maintain optimal growing conditions. The pollination process involved meticulous procedures, including emasculating and precise anther transfer for the crosses. Data collection encompassed various growth parameters and crossability-related traits. Data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA with the cross as a fixed factor in SPSS version 20. Pearson's correlation was used to assess relationships between morphological characters and crossability, the interrelations among morphological characters, and the influence of parental traits on crossability.

Results and discussion

Plants displayed high variability in crossability traits, with coefficients of variation ranging from 31.40 in the number of flowers crossed (NFC) to 77.43% in the percentage of pod set. Reciprocal crosses showed a mean of 6.13 flowers crossed/plant, 0.87 pod set, 12.43% pod set, and 9.71 cm average pod length, with high variability similar to direct crosses (CV = 37.42; 85.76%). (Tables 1 and 2). The correlation analyses (Tables 3 to 6) revealed significant positive correlations between various crossability traits. Similar positive correlations were observed for the reciprocal crosses. The findings revealed considerable variability in crossability traits, particularly in the number of pods set, percentage of pod set, and average seed weight. These results are similar to the findings of Ajayi *et al.* (2020) in cowpea and Gbadamosi *et al.* (2023) in tomato.

Figure 1: Cross-pollinated cowpea in the screen house with tags

Table 1. Crossability traits for the direct cross (SAMPEA-20T × TVu-17327)

Trait	PPS		APL	ASW			
	NFC	NPS (%)	(cm)	ASPP	(g)	NDM	
Number	15	15	15	15	15	15	
Min	4.00	1.00	11.10	10.30	7.00	0.10	37.00
Max	10.00	3.00	50.00	19.20	17.00	0.40	46.00
Sum	97	21	366.90	171.50	147.00	2.36	487.00

NFC: Number of flowers crossed; Number of pods set; Percentage of pods set; Average pod length; Average seeds per pod; Average seed weight; Number of days to pod maturity

Table 2. Crossability traits for the reciprocal crosses (TVu-17327 × SAMPEA-20T) for accessions of cowpea

Trait	NFC	NPS	PPS (%)	APL (cm)	ASPP	ASW (g)	NDM
Number	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
Min	4.00	1.00	12.50	10.00	8.00	0.10	38.00
Max	9.00	2.00	25.00	18.20	16.00	0.20	44.00
Sum	92.00	13.00	186.50	145.70	121.00	1.40	405.00
Mean	6.13	0.87	12.43	9.71	8.07	0.09	27.00
Standard error	0.59	0.19	2.55	1.94	1.64	0.02	5.12
Coefficient of variation (%)	37.41	85.76	79.43	77.37	78.61	83.16	73.45

NFC: Number of flowers crossed; Number of pods set; Percentage of pods set; Average pod length; Average seeds per pod; Average seed weight; Number of days to pod maturity

Table 3. Pearson's correlation analyses among crossability traits of accessions of cowpea for SAMPEA-20T × TVu-17327

Trait	NFC	NPS	PPS	APL	ASPP	ASW	NDM
NFC	1	0.06	-0.51	-0.13	-0.14	0.25	-0.5
NPS		1	0.85**	0.67**	0.76**	0.43	0.73
PPS			1	0.63*	0.72**	0.43	0.66**
APL				1	0.88**	0.74**	0.94**
ASPP					1	0.59*	0.89**
ASW						1	0.77**
NDM							1

*: Significant at $P \leq 0.05$; **: Significant at $P \leq 0.01$

NFC: Number of flowers crossed; Number of pods set; Percentage of pods set; Average pod length; Average seeds per pod; Average seed weight; Number of days to pod maturity

Table 4. Pearson's correlation analyses among crossability traits of accessions of cowpea for TVu-17327 × SAMPEA-20T

Trait	NFC	NPS	PPS	APL	ASPP	ASW	NDM
NFC	1	0.68	0.49	0.54*	0.55*	0.31	0.54*
NPS		1	0.92**	0.87**	0.87**	0.60*	0.84**
PPS			1	0.93**	0.90**	0.79**	0.92**
APL				1	0.85**	0.85**	0.95**
ASPP					1	0.72**	0.93**
ASW						1	0.90**
NDM							1

*: Significant at $P \leq 0.05$; **: Significant at $P \leq 0.01$

NFC: Number of flowers crossed; NPS: Number of pods set; PPS: Percentage of pods set; APL: Average pod length; ASPP: Average seeds per pod; ASW: Average seed weight; NDM: Number of days to pod maturity

Table 5. Pearson's correlation analysis for the influence of SAMPEA-T20 on the crossability traits of accessions of cowpea for the crosses SAMPEA-20T × TVu-17327

Trait	NFC	NPS	PPS	APL	ASPP	ASW	NDM
EM	0.92**	0.87**	0.79**	0.46	0.76**	0.39	0.8
PH	0.36	0.41	0.76**	0.51*	0.25	0.01	0.33
NL	0.42	0.85**	0.67**	0.47	0.99**	0.1	0.41
NMB	0.73**	0.02	0.08	0.19	0.01	0.86**	0.25
TLL	0.07	0.11	0.04	0.24	0.05	0.77	0.16
TLW	0.57*	0.42	0.36	0.54*	0.18	0.6	0.6
DFF	0.53*	0.89**	0.57*	0.99**	0.39	0.55*	0.98**
TNF	0.39	0.27	0.76**	0.19	0.68**	0.24	0.42

*: Significant at $P \leq 0.05$; **: Significant at $P \leq 0.01$. EM: Emergence percentage; PH: Plant height; NL: Number of leaves; NMB: Number of main branches; TLL: Terminal leaflet length; TLW: Terminal leaflet width; DFF: Days to first flowering; TNF: Total number of flowers; NFC: Number of flowers crossed; NPS: Number of pods set; PPS: Percentage of pods set; APL: Average pod length; ASPP: Average seeds per pod; ASW: Average seed weight; NDM: Number of days to pod maturity.

Table 6. Pearson's correlation analysis for the influence of SAMPEA-T20 on the crossability traits of accessions of cowpea for the crosses TVu-17327 × SAMPEA-20T

Trait	NFC	NPS	PPS	APL	ASPP	ASW	NDM
EM	0.43	0.13	0.05	0.03	0.4	0.06	0.12
PH	0.05	0.17	0.23	0.49	0.15	0.89**	0.37
NL	0.68**	0.73**	0.46	0.41	0.96	0.87**	0.85**
NMB	0.59*	0.82**	0.77**	0.71**	0.85**	0.65**	0.67**
TLL	0.06	0.04	0.06	0.02	0.02	0.13	0.04
TLW	0.35	0.93**	0.97**	0.72**	0.86**	0.97**	0.76**
DFF	0.3	0.72**	0.42	0.64*	0.32	0.75**	0.57*
TNF	0.16	0.27	0.41	0.14	0.61	0.5	0.37

*: Significant at $P \leq 0.05$; **: Significant at $P \leq 0.01$. EM: Emergence percentage; PH: Plant height; NL: Number leaves; NMB: Number of main branches; TLL: Terminal leaflet length; TLW: Terminal leaflet width; DFF: Days to first flowering; TNF: Total number of flowers; NFC: Number of flowers crossed; NPS: Number of pods set; PPS: Percentage of pods set; APL: Average pod length; ASPP: Average seeds per pod; ASW: Average seed weight; NDM: Number of days to pod maturity

Results and Discussion

The findings highlight the significance of emergence percentage, plant height, leaf-related traits, terminal leaflet characteristics, flowering timing, and floral abundance in determining the success of hybridization in cowpeas. The positive correlations observed indicate that optimizing germination conditions, enhancing plant architecture, and fine-tuning flowering characteristics can collectively contribute to improved pod set, seed development, and overall maturity.

These insights are instrumental for cowpea breeding programs, offering a nuanced understanding of factors

that influence successful hybridization. Breeding efforts can be tailored to prioritize traits such as germination efficiency, specific plant morphologies, and flowering characteristics to enhance overall crop productivity. It is crucial to acknowledge the context-specific nature of these correlations; as different genetic backgrounds or environmental conditions may influence trait interactions. Therefore, a targeted and context-aware approach is essential for harnessing these correlations effectively in breeding programs. This study advances our understanding of the intricate relationships between quantitative and crossability traits in cowpea, providing a foundation for future research and breeding strategies

aimed at developing resilient and high-yielding cowpea varieties. It is important to consider both genetic and morphological factors in breeding programs to enhance cowpea productivity and resilience to biotic stresses, contributing to sustainable agricultural practices in Nigeria. The hybrids derived from the crosses are recommended for their performance assessment in the F₁, F₂, and subsequent generations focusing on identifying specific traits associated with pod borer resistance and susceptibility, as well as their influence on overall cowpea productivity.

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